

10:00 - 11:30	Session 3: High-Redshift Galaxies	Chair: Harry Ferguson (STSCI)
10:00 - 10:30	3a Invited Talk: Rebecca Bowler (Univ. of Oxford)	Invited Talk
10:30 - 10:45	3b Micaela Bagley (Univ. of Texas)	Going deep with Roman: the $z>9$ UV luminosity function
10:45 - 11:00	3c Isak Wold (NASA/GSFC)	Lya Emitters at Cosmic Dawn with a Deep Roman Grism Survey
11:00 - 11:15	3d Anton Koekemoer (STScI)	Ultra Deep Field Science with the Roman Space Telescope
11:15 - 11:30	3e Gourav Khullar (Univ of Chicago)	The Brightest Galaxy in the $z>5$ Universe: Observing Distant Lensed Galaxies with RST
11:30 - 12:00	3f James Rhoads (NASA/GSFC)	SIT Talk

Session 3 live captioning on Tuesday, 6 October 2020

Note: The invited talk by **Rebecca Bowler** was not recorded or captioned at the request of the speaker.

Harry: Welcome back everybody. We are in the session here and we are going to the second talk. If you can bring your slide up that would be great. I will give you a two-minute warning at 10 minutes. This talk is by **Micaela Bagley**, University of Texas, take it away.

Micaela: Thank you. And thank you to the organizers for the opportunity to speak today. I'm really excited to be here. I will be talking today about some early results on a project related to the luminosity function. This is a project I am working on with Stephen and with the cosmic team which is led by James. I would also like to highlight them for their work, creating the mock catalog that we are using for this project. Measurements of the end of the luminosity function require really deep data and the deepest point tanks that we have with Hubble are the spread to your field and the corresponding parallels. These represent just a handful and they are still significant variance in the measurements between the measurements in these fields. As to be seen and this figure, it shows the luminosity function seven and eight and a selection of these fields and the measurements are color-coded by fields. You can see what kinds of -- the level of the variation that exists field to field here. This variance, or I guess the cause for this variance is well illustrated in this figure from the 2014 which shows a shift of multi-dark stimulation with survey areas from well-known surveys shown for scale. There are the single-point inks from fields as well as others. And while the density variation, the higher shift will be different than what is shown here, this figure is showing that single-point tanks or small area surveys has the possibility to be sitting in over or over danced region while a much larger area can smooth out over those variations. Roman gives us the incredible opportunity to achieve the depth, but in a much larger area. And measurements of the luminosity function are especially crucial in the context of reorganization and understanding they contribution of galaxy. The specific luminosity density is determined by luminosity function down to limiting magnitude. This is often minus 13. And then under assumptions and models accounting for the ionizing proton production efficiency and the escape from galaxies, this can be converted into essentially the ionizing budget that is available from galaxies during that compared to that which is needed to initiate and maintain the process. That is

shown here in this figure by Robert Seminole, it's showing the density as a function of the magnitude and the greater region indicates what region, where galaxies are capable of maintaining the process of that. The Widefield are crucial in making these measurements because any uncertainties and the luminosity function and measurements will directly and strongly affect the luminosity density and any conclusions we draw from these measurements. For this project we are using a catalog constructed using the analytic model. The base for this catalog is a two square degree cone that is constructed from the smaller multi-dark simulation. And so -- I can't claim to be very familiar with how they are constructed, but the idea is that you sort of passed through the simulated volume on multiple lines of sight, create a catalog that gives these sources synthetic positions and it accounts for the effects of any survey geometry. It takes the two square degree cone and estimates dark matter halo histories and simulates the properties of galaxies within those halos. These physical properties are the forward models to create synthetic cytometry in the Roman. Aaron Young has extensively invented this performance at high risk, so I urge you to check out his papers and reach out to him for more information. With this mock catalog, our goal is to compare measurements of the luminosity function and individual fields that are the sizes of Hubble and the Roman fields of view. We are extracting nonoverlapping fields that corresponds to those two sizes. In the two square degrees we are able to get about 1500 fields of view, but only six Roman fields because they are much larger. With these -- so now what we are going to do and each individual field is measure the luminosity function. In the galaxies in a magnitude, we want to compare the measurements that we can get from a Hubble sized field and a Roman size field. We do have to artificially extend the depth of the mock catalog which I will explain in a minute. Finally, we fed a function via the maximum likelihood analysis and compare the measurements. I would like to note here that at this stage we are not applying any survey selection functions to the catalog. We plan to do that at the next step of this project. At this stage we are sort of working under 100% completed and 0% contamination for the analysis. The approximate completeness limit of the mock catalog is a magnitude of minus 18.5. As I mentioned we want to be doing this analysis down to the depth. We scale, extending the depth that we reach with these mock observations. The way we do this is we take the function to the full cone and we scale it down to the density of each individual field. This gives us the number of galaxies and each magnitude that are protected by the luminosity function we then perturb those predicted numbers by N and refit the function. Okay. Now we get to move on to some results here. What I'm showing here is the positions of all of the sources for the mock catalog between 6.5 and 7.5. You can see that there are quite a few variations if you look on the small scale. To illustrate this you can envision extracting or measuring the luminosity function in two fields. One on the left is in a region, under dense region and the other is the over danced region. The luminosity functions that are measured in these two fields are shown in the figures where the Schechter fits end of the data is the orange line. In both cases the luminosity function that we measure are quite different and neither one reflects the black curves which shows the luminosity function measured in the full cone. However, if you them make the same measurement in the same region, but with the Roman field of view you get the measurement shown and purple here. Their huge improvement. And they have now been able to essentially recover the true, very closely recover the true luminosity function measured in this volume. What I'm showing here are the luminosity functions that we have measured and six, seven and eight. And in the fit to the full light cone is shown as the white curve. The densities are stars here. We are showing the individual measurements from fields as squares for Roman fields in small circles. The 100% range, again, only six Roman fields, but the full range of the measurements from those fields are shown and purple. And the 95 and 60% range for the fields are shown in orange. Here you can see of course that the luminosity functions measured from the large Roman fields are much closer to the true value, and this case, whereas the HST field has a huge amount of variation, more than an order of magnitude and density. What we are seeing here is evidence that this Widefield is smoothing out over the local variations. 2 minutes left. Thank you. Here I'm showing the distributions of the Schechter parameters to best fit the individual field. From left to right, I'm showing the characteristic density, characteristic magnitude, and the slope. The value measured from the full light cone is the vertical black line and to the Roman distribution is shown and purple and the distribution that is shown in orange. Again, as we are seeing, sort of the moral of the story year. The Roman distributions are very narrow and tight compared to the HST distribution. I'm also showing this black line showing the agency distribution or the distribution measured an agency field after I impose a very strict cut. It shows that the variation that we are seeing from the measurement is not dominated by, is not necessarily dominated by uncertainties. It is dominated by spatial variations in these field to field variations in the light cone. Our last step is to turn these luminosity function measurements into the luminosity density. Here I'm showing plots of the nonionizing luminosity density which I got by integrating the luminosity function down to an absolute magnitude of minus 13. Which is, I've done an integration down to - 15 and 17 for reference, but all of the color ranges are for integrating down to - 13. We see a wide variation of what that measurement is from HST field spirit on the left figure, it is showing that value of the function with the three we have measured so far. On the right at issue in

the distribution of the UB luminosity density in six and seven. Excuse me. And the numbers that are shown there on that figure represents sort of an estimate, the fractional error of these two measurements. We can see the HST field ranges from almost a 45% to 65% fractional certainty, while the Roman fields are much closer to 10% or less than 10%. This is showing that a Roman is going to allow us to, this is sort of quantifying what kind of an improvement we are going to be able to get with measurements related to the UB luminosity function with these very wide fields of view. We are really excited about where this project is going for some of the next steps. Our first next step is to sort of measure the luminosity function. To do this we will add photometric scatter to the mock light according to a couple of different steps. We will add selection functions to approximate a survey and then calculate the completeness and contamination that results from that. We also plan to do some trade studies where possible Roman deep field exploring filter combinations, different depth and areas and investigating what kind of impact each of the area has on measurements related to the luminosity function such as the integrated luminosity density and again the implications that that have for reionization. Finally I want to leave you with this table of a number of accounts we are predicting based on this analysis. In the right column here the numbers are shown for what we observe in the light cone down to the approximate limit. And the next two columns show the numbers that were protecting by extending that luminosity function down to the depth and then the depth for a proposed Roman field where this proposal, it is presented in the white paper in 2019 and also see Anton talk later in this session. Of course the Roman numbers are huge by comparison, but I find them mind bogglingly exciting which what we can do with one Roman pointing. Thank you. I can take questions.

Great. Thank you. We don't have a lot of time. I would encourage people to write questions on slack. Let me just throw out a quick one. I noticed in your slide 13 which is over there on the left. Like in Rebecca's talk, it seems like the models prefer something that isn't turning over at the bright and quite as deeply as Schechter. Have you tried to fit the full model function and does it prefer a Schechter or a double power law?

We have not yet done that. It does seem to be the case that it's deeper than what would be predicted for a Schechter function.

Thanks. Let me encourage you to go to the slack. There are a bunch of questions. I'm looking at the time and we will have to move on.

Next is **Isak Wold**. If you can get your slides up. He is at NASA Goddard space flight center and he will talk about Lyman alpha Emitters.

Isak: I'm going to be talking about our simulations of the deep Roman survey at because McDonald. This is work I'm doing with James and Toby and the cosmic dawn. The simulations were actually originally done by Toby and I was in charge of looking for emitters and now I have taken over both roles, simulating and recovering. To motivate the simulations I'm going to first talk about the latest results from the survey. This is the project, a very Widefield 24 square degree survey looking for these objects at a ratio of 6.9. The survey takes advantage of dark energy cameras, uniquely sensitivity in the infrared as well as a custom-made filter probing a very narrow slice. These tests, looking at the neutral hydrogen fraction take advantage of the fact that their resident lay scattered by any anything they encounter, making them sensitive to the ionization state. And our latest results based on 150 galaxies found within four out of the eight fields find a neutral hydrogen fraction ranging anywhere from about 37% to 0%. This is shown on the figure on the left. And so this is a neutral hydrogen fraction that is consistent with a zero. To detect the onset of reionization and a nonzero neutral hydrogen fraction, we would like to probe to higher redshift and this becomes inefficient on the ground. What we really need is a space-based instrument capable of probing a large volume to a wide range area. And this is where the telescope can play a major role. I have a wide capability that can survey emitters greater than seven. It's in space so there is no interference from bright skylines which is very problematic for ground-based surveys, Roman emitters will be observed with a single instrument with the systematics that are present in the surveys. And our initial simulations show that a 70 hour survey can reach that. This is what I will be discussing for the remainder of this talk, these deep simulations for Roman. Here is the slide that sets up the input for the grism simulations. We started off with an actual observed field. On the far left, the Cosmo field observed with Hubble. We use these with constraints to not only simulate Roman direct images, but Roman grism images. And so

here I am showing two out of the 25 different position angles that are all observing the same field of view, just add a different orientation. And so here on the far right I am listing some of the set up parameters for the simulations. So for the deepest survey that we are considering, we are simulating 25 different independent angles, each of which has an exposure time of ten to kill a this is where we get a total exposure time of 70 hours. We are assuming for the simulations a background level of .5. A single-chip field of view, however this slide is just showing a fourth of that. We are simulating all the objects that are brighter than 25.5 A.D., for these current simulations we are using the Hubble, but we are working to incorporate a more realistic Roman. The simulations are done with the latest development, we are not just simulating the science order, the order spectra, we are simulating the zero and order spectra. So here are just, here I am highlighting some of the objects that we are simulating. If we were to look at the spectrum, this is a relatively bright star that has a continuum spectrum. There are many galaxies and then we have also inputted fake, fake that span the range of locks. An immediate goal of the simulations is to characterize Roman's ability to detect these emitters. Here is the detailed parameter set up that we are using to run the simulations and the assumptions that we are making one we are simulating that the elf mentors. The latest development is that we are not just simulating the client's orders, are also simulating the order and the second order spectra. Here's a slide showing the different spectra orders that we are simulating. This is the noiseless direct image. This is the zero next to it. And then the science order, and finally the second order spectra. We are simulating these images without any noise. We combine all three of these orders and then we apply the noise for the exposure time we are interested in. To highlight kind of the implications of this. Here I am showing a bright star circled in red in this simulated direct image. We can see that it's traced, it's shown by this red line that hopefully everyone can see. However, if we look at this other position angle, just observe the different, different orientation, we can see that now the trace is shown here at an angle of 43 degrees. Here are just some other, here is a bright galaxy that is highlighted in blue. Here's a green star that highlighted its trace and green. You can see here that in the position angle of 0 degrees, the red and green star have overlapping spectra, however in general this will not be the case when we observe the same field in a different position angle. We can disentangle these overlapping objects. This is the strategy behind this multi-position angle, observational strategy. The way we are conducting, reduction, the search for these emitters as we are constructing a data queue. We know the weight length dispersion and the trace that characterized these grism images. We can extract a spectrum for any spatial position that we are interested in and to form a data cube consisting of two spatial axes. We produce data cubes for each position angle and then they combine them all. In our deepest survey we will have 25 different position angles, 25 data cubes and we combine them all to remove overlap from neighboring sources. To illustrate this in more detail, if we zoom in on the small field of view, this is the field of view, here I am showing the noiseless direct image chose to show the more fainter objects that we are simulating. On the right I am cycling through the wavelength range of the final data cube, a wavelength range of 1.27-1.28 microns. What we do with this final data cube is weak page through the wavelengths looking for a mission object and in this case we have, we find a strong emission feature at 1.277 microns. This is a simulated all flat matter at 9.5. And so what we would like to answer is, how are we able, what's our ability to recover these objects at a function. That is shown in this completeness plot. This is the fraction of recovered emitters as a function of flux, line flux. And so for our deepest stimulation which has a total of 70 hours of exposure distributed over 25 different position angles we find this black curve, which indicates that we can recover, we can reach line deaths comparable to the deepest survey. On the order of ten to the negative 17. The red and blue curves that are shown within this plot are exploring different observational trade-offs. In both cases the red end of the blue curve, we are keeping the total exposure time constant and just altering the number of angles. And what we are finding is that given our reduction strategy we find increased returns when we have more position angles. As shown by the higher red curve compared to the blue curve. 3 minutes. Thanks. What we are working on with these simulations now is to produce -- with the simulations we have produced a realistic background scene and then we have done this in order to test our ability to recover emitters. This can be useful for many different applications but we are working to provide the tools needed to insert your object of interest within a realistic extragalactic scene. This is one thing we are working on. The other thing we are working on is to produce a data challenge for the community. Provided with our multiposition angle simulations, how well can you are favorite production software recover line emitters? This is the way in which we are doing it, this data search method, which I have previously employed on data. This is, one of the advantages of this is it does not require a detection and allows us to make a more fair comparison to the surveys which are also not selected. There are other alternative software is out there and it would be interesting to compare the advantages and disadvantages of variance, various procedures. Okay breadth and summary, Roman's ability to obtain deep near infrared spectra will allow us to measure the evolution of a luminosity function greater than seven. This will provide us with ionization measurements of the intergalactic medium at because McDonnell. Our work demonstrates that a 70 hour grism survey with a

realistic foreground scene can achieve Lya depths comparable to the nearest survey. This is what we need to constrain the evolution of the number density for these objects. For our future work we are releasing a data challenge and we will provide an extragalactic background scene. I can take questions.

Thank you very much. We have a first question appearing. I think you might have touched on this. Have you looked into extracting sources which are not detected? Sources with emission?

Right. That is one of the main advantages of this data cube search mechanism. Many different reduction software requires you to have prior knowledge of the continuum source. By going through the data cube and just selecting on a mission line, in fact, and our final data cube we have a step in which we subtract off the continuum. We are trying to just, what we are doing is recovering a flux limited, an example of objects. And so that is one of the main advantages of doing this data cube search method which we have shown with the data we can outperform their standard pipeline reduction, which is continuum selected and do a better job of comparing to samples.

Thanks. He mentioned the data challenge. Do you have a timescale in mind for one you might kick that off? We would like to have this presented to the community by the end of the year.

Great. We will have to move on. Thank you very much. Please go to the slack channel, there can be further discussion there.

We will move on to **Anton Koekemoer**. He is from a space telescope and he'll be talking about ultra deep field science.

Anton: Thanks, everybody. Thanks for all the great talk so far. I'm going to continue the theme so far talking about an observational approach to the programs and where we might be able to go with it. Much of this comes from the Astro 2020 white paper. We submitted this early last year which came out of the working group. This is actually open. Anyone who is interested, we can include. Basically the gist of this is if you start from the initial perspective of science for the space observatory, the observational galaxy is to drive the space, so magnitudes greater than 26 or so. you need about point one to resolve any substructure. Even while this gives good deep imaging, it won't be high resolution, something of the quality to do this. Yesterday, they showed some more graphical summaries of the different tiers that we have worked with in this area. I have summarized them more detail here. Three categories of area depth year, first of all, the smallest. With HST, the field service. We will start in 95 and then of course the field and the last decade and a half. Also with grism. These single surveys are what leads us to this. We tend to reach 29 or 30. The fields don't reach, but they do go a factor of ten deep. I will come back to that point later. Medium depth surveys tend to kind of be the next level up. A factor of may be a couple of hundred larger, so if you hundred square. 27.5, 28 or so in-depth. And these tend to be larger, goods and so forth. And then the larger survey, with grism I want to mention there as well. They tend to reach your typical, 27.5. These three tiers show the plot yesterday from -- from the science working group of 2012 which set the foundation for the field. I mentioned of course this study is quite dated now, but the content remains come updated numbers, especially Rebecca's nice talk earlier today and also Michaela's, and the others you heard. The basic plot we are looking at here is really how deep you go as a function of area. A very simple key mode of area depth plot with surveys like the shallow end of things. The horizontal axis shows you the limit or the exposure time which corresponds around 27 or so magnitude for about an hour. And the vertical axis shows the area covered. So reaching up to the scale on the top part of the plot. On the right, this is part of the data, relevant enough, I will show you the counts. Notably, the surveys, we tend to find in order, 9-10 galaxies. Appears to be several dozen, several hundred, and you extend that when you go to the larger survey. Where to next? The next step is twofold, obviously we will go deeper, 31-32, planning these. And I expect we will be able to reach those depths fairly easily. You would expect 31.5-32 points still. -- compared to that. It is comparable to HST. You have the same kind of -- and as we have seen in various studies with the number counts, things like the galaxy luminosity. This is where Roman comes in, expanding the space by two orders. You are single point during same three categories of fields in the previous table, but now a factor of a hundred. Your ultra point instead of a few square minutes can now reach a degree scale. In the medium-sized is bigger, ten square degrees and the large area -- covering that much more. This is the graphic you have seen in Romans talk on a Monday, comparing if we take the

sum total of our candles UDF, XT F, you see the five candle fields, superposed skill. You can cover all of these. I will note here that the total time investment, XT F. You talk about a few thousand orbits whereas with Roman you could cover not quite that depth, but still reach the same kind of area. If you want to revisit that plot of area depth, Roman would do for us. It effectively instead of going down a number counts for these deep surveys, you increase everything up to a few thousand square minutes with Roman. You are reaching 29 or even 30. A substantial fraction of the square degree. This is the 2012 count that they showed much nicer versions. Basically instead of a handful, the reaching of order, several hundred easily of candidates for this field. And as Michaela showed you, you can get several thousand, maybe even 15,000 or so. This will be a spectacular increase and parameters. Looking at observation, one of the deeper -- this is what feeds the numbers that Micaela mentioned. If you look at the effect of areas, this is from Rachel's paper, the plot on the left, it's actually a very efficient telescope. Essentially taking the camera three and in fact even more centered. Your filters here can reach, fairly reasonable exposure times, this table, covering about 300 or so hours of total time investment. This was fine tuned to reach similar depth. You may want to go deeper in the blue filters to provide better dropout out of the activity. Certainly of order, 30-point something magnitude can be required. Except for the very reddest one, the table has a misprint, but F184. It's a bit shallower. Almost 31st magnitude. What are the science motivations? I won't attempt to cover them here. I think in today's session there is an excellent talk, Micaela Rebecca, and Isak as well. Very interesting numbers, several hundred at least 9-11. Possibly 12 or 13, depending on how we do the shoulder selection. You can really revolutionize instead of a few hundred galaxies you can have a few hundred thousand. The black hole, coevolution, the samples are typically a few hundred. We will expect to get several tens of thousands, 2-6. And even things like large-scale structures, taking the size with a couple of square degrees and extending it to a few magnitudes deeper. We can probe the structure and environment, a very fine limit. And finally the supernova, much of it will be done with the high latitude survey. Even with this which we will cover a degree or so. You can do some interesting models as well. And any other favorites you can think of. Categories of deep field programs, how would we do this? I mentioned a couple that are probably not going to be workable to begin with, but we have things on Roman which will be the core surveys. The supernova field, too wide and too shallow. Probably not an optical mix of depth. Maybe parallels, so another category is calibration field, it will go back time and time again. We may be able to, but we will be focusing on calibrations. Really the third category I think is a new kind of observing program. Either as a Geo or other program or may be some special type of program with Roman. It could live within the wider fields. And also including a deep grism here, much more detail. In terms of imaging, there are a few things we can do here. You can either place it at a different location, 300 hours each with total investments. Different locations, if you make them continuous that would enable the talk, you look at large-scale structure and environment much more cleanly in the field, especially if you want to have deep prism overlay on that. You can also consider putting them in different locations. May be if you have hemisphere action issues come obviously one in the north and one in the South, they'll be the logical choice. The South would optimize ALMA and the North would optimize other. That would be part of the considerations for where to put them. If we do couple them in the fields, we do end up constraining the fields location somewhat more. The supernova fields for the programs will be much more official. There it would be driven to the north, things like the north field survey. That is a program done by Roger. That can be one candidate. In the South, if it's a supernova, it will probably be in the northern field. That could be a better candidate. extension, if you want to stay out of it you end up driven to -- ultimately you are joined in four categories. You've the Galactic if you want to avoid both Zodi. These four categories will play together in terms of what kind of locations for Roman. If we tie these two, this drives us to any of the current four Ruben fields. A note here that none of the existing Ruben Euclid -- they would be precluded for supernova fields. On the other hand there been a couple of proposals, late 2018 in response to the Ruben field call to propose a couple of additional fields either in the south or possibly in the north. The Ruben fields, a southern field. And in the north you can see Euclid. We could alternatively -- in that case you are much freer to choose other fields. Especially if you want to go deep to 30. The polar fields, they tend to be fields that are somewhat better studied, have better data. They aren't always accessible. These tend to be more amenable to both hemispheres, but more strict in terms of how often you can observe them. Near fields are always possible and I mentioned that, but I think ultradeep, you want to lie somewhere with the data that we haven't had. To summarize this, we could accommodate in more than one category. We could accommodate the medium survey which would fall on top of supernova. Or we could proceed with these other field surveys, in that case we would decouple from the supernova fields. In this case, adding significant depth increase across several bands, beyond what you need to. And your locations will be driven more by the data. Less by a need for it. On the other hand if you do want to do a deep grism program that might put you back to continued. Much of this would hinge on how important and how critical the grism find is to a survey. Basically four categories of constraints, Galactic and ecliptic. I will finish off ear with the next step. It's conceivable that field with

Roman could be a spatial left field to lie beyond the typical program. We could consider it as a GO proposal, but we might want to consider a different cause for this field. We could imagine the process to input. We can look at general science drivers. We could look at the observational parameter space. We would look at, look at the synergy with other programs. Things like calibration or supernova fields. And also synergy with items. Overlapping growth and existing fields and also -- that is really why we want to start consolidating and making this robust at this point. I mentioned also here, nonproprietary, Roman. I think for purposes of symmetry and as we heard in their excellent talk yesterday on considerations of access and equity, we may want to suggest that to some of the other facilities will be following up on -- obviously others will have their own categories of the program. If their observations from significant investments of time, we may want to suggest to those that participate, maybe have a special category of nonproprietary. In terms of a community process possibly to enable this, we have community workshops, observatory initiatives. Similar to the fields model which I think followed a pretty well-established and very successful process. They led an external working group, conveying some committee, advisors Institute or the project on what kind of options to proceed. In recommend other proposals. These are kind of the implementation questions for how we would make a program work. I think today's session we can focus on the science simulations. I will leave you with these thoughts. I think the questions, we can either talk about integration. I would be happy to answer questions on what science we could do that hasn't been covered yet by Micaela or Rebecca or any other observational parameters. Thank you.

We are going to have to move on to the next talk. Let's continue discussion with this interesting topic in the thread on slack. Thanks again.

We will move on to **Gourav Khullar** from University of Chicago who will talk about the brightest galaxy in the red shift.

Gourav: Thank you so much. I'm grateful to have this opportunity to speak with you all. I'm super excited to hear all he talks, specifically because Rebecca - and Anton have set my talk really well. I use he/and pronouns. I will talk about the brightest galaxy in the Roman space telescope. I will use these as an anchor to have conversations with you all. I'm going to be describing a new project that we've been working on here at the University of Chicago. The physics of the galaxy and use that as an anchor to talk about the Roman Space Telescope, galaxy specifically projections on a number of galaxies. How do we understand stellar populations in these Heisey galaxies and last but not least, how do we harness the Roman spatial resolution? I'm happy to talk more about this, any of these topics over slack or during the conference for the discussion. I'm going to dive right in. I'm here today representing a new collaboration project. This is the Chicago league located at the public service. We are in an effort to find strong gravitational lenses and recent public imaging data. This is going to be the survey and the pan star survey, we are looking for objects that are on the margins of distributions of color. We have done examinations of the 275 lines of sight. One of the more fascinating parts of this projects is that, it was initiated as a focus of an undergraduate research class that started in December last year. I'm here to talk about some of the latest work that we are publishing. I was the lead grad student for this project and here are some of the undergraduates and collaborators of the collaboration. I'm here at the moment talking about an extraordinary bright lens galaxy. What we did as part of the examination search and the color magnitude search, we found a galaxy that was essentially a classic galaxy, cluster super bright galaxy. We found this in the data. This is part of a comprehensive vision search and they search for about 4,000 square degrees for the potential lens. This was one of those objects. We did follow-up the span imaging. What I'm showing here on the top right is essentially a spectrum. The interesting part here as you can see an orange is there is no law. Essentially bright. 20.5. We do a basic for the survey based on the data and emission line spectrum that we have. We find the galaxy with the flat, very little continuation. And why is this exciting to talk about? One, it's a super bright galaxy, but also when we fit for a bunch of different parameters, one of the strongest constraints we get is on the total stellar mass. And the reason for that is essentially have a galaxy and it's only been a billion years since this galaxy was spawned and there is not been enough time for all the stars to get their light and reprocess in the portion of the spectrum. Basically what I'm showing here is essentially a star history constraint based on ground-based, ground imaging based lens modeling with a stellar mass of 10.1 and a rate of 20. What does this have to do with the Roman Space Telescope? One of the things that I think I'm super excited about and this has been mentioned in many talks over the last day and a half is the white area coverage with a spatial resolution. This is going

to be a unique resource for discovery and characterization of the strongly lensed galaxies in the early universe. I'm quite interested to learn more about how this will fill the discovery gap between superbright systems found in shallower data, something that Rebecca's talk alluded to, and the faintest lens systems that have been found in the survey. What I want to talk about today is combining the features or the aspirational features of the Roman space telescope to resolving power of the strong gravitational lensing. There are two main things to talk about, capturing the UV optical signatures from stellar populations as well as observing the very interiors of the galaxy to talk about low star rates and skills approximately less than one. What I wanted to hear really quickly is an order of magnitude calculation. How many lens galaxies will it find at five? This is the luminosity function, we've seen this many times today. Let's zoom in to the other portion of this. What I've done here is, this is the luminosity function, numbers, number of galaxies, density, magnitude, volume as a function of absolute. What I do here is I put the galaxy that I just described on this, both in the image plane and the resource plane. I also mark the limited magnitude based on the projections that we have so far. I map the absolute magnitude to the apparent magnitude and basically do the following. I assume a flat distribution, a similar attribution and the magnification in this part of the universe and we ask a simple question. If this is a difficult object, how many more objects can we find in the proposal in the survey? It's still very instructive. This is how. What we do is we calculate the area from, you know, mapping the number of galaxies that are basically faded and the magnitude limit, but would be propped up into the observed, propped up brighter than the magnitude limit. And what we effectively find is a set number of objects. What I do here is the comparison between the details here, the area that was surveyed by COOL-LAMPS and the Roman high latitude survey, approximately 2,000 degrees. What we effectively find is that we see about anywhere between 30600 galaxies at registered 5-6 that are lensed and relative to the limits of the service. What I'm actually talking about here is the example of the lens galaxies with, you know, infrared imaging. That can tell us a lot about what these objects look like. As I said, this is super accrued and these numbers can vary by a factor of a few come up with the interesting part here is what we definitely know is that Roman is going to be seeing these galaxies. This will create a sample of these extraordinary galaxies into the observed magnitude limit beyond the magnitude limit for Roman and would definitely -- it's not something that they would be able to follow up exactly, but a high latitude survey by Roman, you would be able to basically get all this data. So how do we go about characterizing the properties of such galaxies? We ran a few tests. We created a synthetic galaxy with an SED using a ratio of three, galaxy which will be seen in the highlighted survey, a ratio of a hunter which is a superbright galaxy. The current star provision rate is 0-20. What we do is we pull synthetic imaging from projected Rubin Observatory and the band from the Roman Space Telescope. What you are seeing here is essentially an attempt to see what we get back if we fit these galaxies using what we have today. This is a star formation history -- thank you. This is a star formation rate, the truth values are in, the truth values are in green. The analysis products both from accuracy and precision perspective are an orange, gray, and blue. Similarly the corner that you are seeing on the right shows the actual constraints, the distribution of the constraints that we tried to go for. You can see for 100, a superbright galaxy and Roman, you be able to recover accurately and precisely these parameters. Specifically I would like to call your attention to the star mass, the very first. Moving onto the final thread that I want to call, the resolution of Roman and I think this is super exciting to me. For lensed galaxies, the presence of agency quality imaging has proven to be an absolute key to unlocking precise lensed models. You want to be able to reliably the magnifying galaxy back to the source. And specific features of both the lens and the source can come in handy in this procedure. What I'm showing here is a galaxy from the survey, a galaxy cluster that is a massive lens. This is from Bayliss. You can clearly see a remarkable difference. For example, in the ground-based imaging you see a bluish arc on the top, but in the -- and the other imaging you are seeing the red arc. Similarly, another example, 0851, you can see that the clump nature of some of these are highlighting the internal structure of these galaxies, only seen in agency like imaging. Trying to draw your attention here to a reddish clump and a reddish arc that was there. It's interesting to see that these are steps that are similarly expected from Rubin, so this is analogous to the data comparison. Here I quickly show what Roman Space Telescope's spatial resolution will allow us to do which is to do a clump by clump structure. This is a plot from Johnson 2017 which is a clump of decomposition. And the exciting part of this is with Roman end of the data we will have at hand, we will be able to do a similar analysis that they showed a couple of minutes ago, clump by clump, which is absolutely exciting. To summarize, what we have in the near future is a large sample of distance in the galaxy with multiband imaging and micron spectra, this is sampling the continuum effectively. The coverage for spatial resolution combined with a strong gravitational and gives us the galaxies as well as signatures for stellar populations. And with that I will stop right here. Please find me on slack if you would like to chat about COOL-LAMPS and the many projects we are running within the collaboration. My other work on star histories with galaxies, the telescope galaxy clusters

examples. As well as anything to do with observations and galaxies. I'm sure we'll be hearing about this tomorrow and tomorrow session. With that I will stop. Thank you so much.

Thank you. We are close out of time. I will ask a want a one. Just to compress it. How much freedom did you get your star formation histories and fitting the bright?

That's a great question. I'm going to quickly go back to that slide. Essentially what we are doing here is using the prescription from Johnson talking specifically about star formation histories. The idea is to use several different bins and a wide variety of star history, we have done similar tests with the star formation histories. As far as, and we retrieved similar results as far as stellar maps are concerned and I'm happy to talk more about a later stage. We have run tests on all sorts of star formation histories to construct.

We will go to **James Rhoads**. The final talk of the session. This will be a 25 minute, five minute per question. James will talk about the team.

James: Thank you. I wanted to talk today about cosmic dawn. This is work we have lead over the years with a number of collaborations, notably today I'll be highlighting results from the team, the cosmic survey team and the investigation team which is now the Nancy Grace science investigation team. I like to ask, one is the last time that a typical baryon did anything exciting? The answer is re-ionization. It was the first time one galaxies had a global impact on the universe around them through their ultraviolet light. If you think about it, today a large fraction of the baryons are still in the medians, that is why this was the last signature day for most of them. It was recognized and the 2010 survey as one of the top three for the decade. Along with new worlds and physics of the universe. And the Nancy Grace telescope course is elated to work on new worlds through its graph and a search for planets. And it's slated to work, study the physics of the universe through a dark energy search which are both the cosmology. We felt it was only fitting that its potential for revolutionizing cosmic Don should also be studied and that was motivation for our investigation team. There are three ways, two main ways of studying the ionization, one is basically the accounting methods. For that you want to count up the sources that produce ultraviolet light and compare that to the number of hydrogen and the recombination of rates for hydrogen. The other approach is direct searches for evidence neutral ionized gas in the early universe. And for that what you need to do is either look for the effects of the ionizing -- sorry. And the effects the ionized material on the background which is scattered and smoothed out over the effects of the neutral material either in a mission which was 21-centimeter search method or the scattering of Lyman alpha. Of course we want to pull all of these methods together to get a complete picture. I'm going to focus on looking for neutral hydrogen. Lyman Alva is a natural result of ongoing star formation in young galaxies. Basically an ionizing proton that's absorbed within the galaxy has a two-thirds chance of producing as a recombination occurs. And it can carry something like 6% of the young galaxy luminosity. That goes back to 1967. And it can afford interesting tests to re-ionization. As I illustrated here at the bottom, a couple of different scenarios. One where you have a young starburst in an ionized medium and a Lyman as the same degree of transfer. I've only drawn protons that are heading towards the observer to say putting down arrows and PowerPoint. If you make that media neutral instead the Lyman protons are scattered and although they eventually stream, a large number, that result is that you suppress the circus brightness, you blur the image of the galaxy in the service brightness down by lowers of magnitude. And that means that it tends to drop out of any survey that has surface brightness. In 2004 we published the first re-ionization test based on that, showing 6.5, it was not predominately neutral at a time when they were still active in what was going on there or the Peterson results. We will come back to the implications a little bit later. First I wanted to detour and high we find the galaxy in the first place. There are two main methods that we use heavily. One is narrowband imaging. For that what we do is you want to take images and both the test band and a broader continuum and you are looking for the objects showing the narrow ends. Those are the ones where there is an admission line. And then to see if it's Lyman or not, our favorite method is to see the distribution and if it's consistent with the red shift with the Lyman alpha. You do that by going to the blue filter. If the method works well, what happens is you find your narrowband source and find the wand out of these four that during turn up in the blue. And then you find a nice admission line. That is that method and we use it from the ground where it's possible to get a dark sky by choosing a wavelength between the emission line. If you want the wider wavelength range is very valuable to go and space bar there you have sort of the ones that have the action process. You take the spectrum, although there is one point

source showing here, this is in fact the dispersed spectrum, a trace going off to the right which is not easy to see, but it is significantly detected. This is the result from the 2016 paper. And then you apply if necessary the same sort of consistency check. To see if it is consistent with the Lyman alpha. I was talking about how neutral gas blurs it between the detection threshold. Here's a link showing that simulation. And you can see the point sources are places where you would be able to see Lyman alpha in 1 degree patch. Black is neutral gas and white is ionized gas. We have apply these techniques from the ground and I want to highlight surveys. First is the LAGER survey, covering 24 square degrees. We expect a total of 400-600 when we finish the observations for all eight fields. We have about 25 confirmed galaxies, so 25 more galaxies than the degree ionization which is a substantial factor of what it is when we started the survey. Six papers were published and a couple more and press and Ann Pratt. We have done this using the 4-meter telescope and the dark energy camera and a custom filter which cost less than my house but more than my car. The team members who are down here at the bottom of the page. I'm going to highlight the collaboration. It's a real nice multinational thing. I'm just going to put up briefly at the list of papers, mostly so it will be there and slides in the video. If anyone wants to screen shot it, do so soon because now I want to start looking at the science results. This is the first result I wanted to highlight, the LAGER re-ionization constraints. On the left, a paper last year. This shows the overall LAGER survey, luminosity function is shown right here at 7.0. You can see here that the survey has become a see basically smooth evolution from 5.7-7.0. The constraint is less certain, but you can see the luminosity density generally is dropping as you go higher. To extract a neutral fraction constraint from that there is multiple methods, but the one that is featured in newspaper and Isaac's upcoming paper is to compare the luminosity density in the line and in the continuum between two broad shifts and you take out the evolution of the galaxy population by using the UV continuum and you see what is left over. And when you do that, he showed this figure from his paper and preparation, but the results, there consistent with the range of neutral hydrogen fractions with about 40%. I also wanted to highlight something you get out of 24 square degrees of survey. This is from the first two survey fields. The Cosmo field in the field south. You can see they 2019 paper, smooth density contours show a couple of substantial over densities. Nothing similar. And there is a statistically different significance in the function between these two. We have incidentally gotten a lot of confirmations, so it's not blue. And if you look at these two primary over densities and Cosmo's and calculate up the UV protein, you should be capable of driving substantial ionized bubbles even without accounting for fainter neighbors. We are doing further analysis in a paper that Weida Hu has submitted and basically studying this region which is what we are calling LAGER over density one. You can see here the map of the neutral regions within that if you want to play with that and see it rotate I put the URL there. To do a recap on LAGER, it's the largest narrowband survey. There are four more in progress. It contains confirmations. And we found evidence for spatially variable luminosity functions, ionized bubbles, protocluster region at the re-ionization. And the results have been tele- graded and journals. This is the only time one of our results has been picked up by a poet to the best of my knowledge. I wanted to change gears to a slightly higher shift and think about the cosmic deep and wide narrowband survey. This is a survey program we have done using the 4-meter telescope. We have covered and total one square degree. It's harder when you have to go with that. Shout out to Roman, that is why we are so excited about what it will do. We have gotten a square degree of narrowband imaging down to minus 17 per second. And of the sort of science so far as papers from Tilvi. This is a small corner of the field. There are three galaxies in a small region that popped up as narrowband excess sources in the data. One is the previously discovered object and the other two are brand-new. And here are a specter of all three of those. And if you take the models that relate come of the luminosity's to the expectance sizes about what they can make in the intergalactic medium, you can draw the conception here of what that ionized region might look like. And the fainter sources are sitting behind the more luminous ones and there is a reasonable chance that it is creating an ionized bubble that helps the elf up from the fainter sources emerge. If you want to show this for your Astro classes, you've got a nice video as part of that in January. This isn't the only ionized bubble that's been reported in the early universe. There are papers in the early LAGER results. This is to our knowledge the highest shift, ionized region that is identified. Okay. That was the narrowband method and now I want to change gears. The reason the spectroscopy from space is twofold, the air glow, the absorption from the atmosphere. Second, spatial resolution boosts the signal. For the first point, it shows across the bottom here the OH omission line and across the top, the absorption. You can see the sort of vertical blue bars, the handful of windows where it's straightforward to get between the OH from the ground. And in some cases you pay a price even there in the water vapor absorption. The specific wavelengths, that is likely to change from the ground. This shows the galaxy sizes across the range from 2-6. You can see here that the median sizes, the heavy black dots are basically not changing all the way across that range. Notably it's a size that is quite small compared with the ground-based, but it's reasonably resolved or semiresolved. We have pursued a series of projects to take advantage of the strengths. The first spectroscopy with the program for extragalactic science. It was a treasury

program, it led the first of 3. And they found a number of interesting things ranging from 12 stars and our galaxy out towards ionization galaxies. This one is the highest signal galaxy and I love showing this because you can see the rate right here as moderate, significant as well as a very clear break. And in addition to its science return, grapes yielded improvements. We worked really hard on the data, they had 16 iterations of data reduction and along the way really refined methods for sky subtraction in searches, calibration, combination angles. And those successes have enabled surveys. Our own surveys, eight more fields and double from the original. Between them these have yielded 30 papers and a number of PhD theses. That uses the grism, the ones highlighted right here. And another from Larson in 2018. These are lines around 7.5. In one case, the first one where we've got both the line and the continuum, the break in the same object is the red shift. And the other is the high equivalent source, about 7.5 showing that there are still high equivalent sources out there. In the last few minutes talk I want to turn to the future and talk about Roman. We've already spoken of the advantages of being the atmosphere and having 300 megapixels. You have the field together with the sensitivity. And this just sketches out the Roman across the simulation showing the point you've heard today. It's really good to have a wide-field and sensitivity when you're trying to do science in the presence of cosmic variance. This is the cosmic dawn team, people who have contributed over the years and the science goals of the team are to basically do a census of Lyman galaxies. Not restricting ourselves just to be the measurement of neutral gas, we are also looking at the census. To place this in context, this is the plank history constraint, fully ionized at the bottom and neutral at the top. And this shows the ridership to range and approximate four LAGER, DAWN and what Roman will be able to do. As far as the galaxies -- Has spoken about this and has referred the reader, the audience back to her talk for those details. We expect to study these large samples of the Lyman galaxies and use them to understand the interplay between environment and galaxy properties. This is now a shout out to the members of the team working on that. This is a figure showing from the work in progress, the spectrum, these are chosen to have the most and distinguishable factors. If you choose the right color, one that includes that, you can see the band, it gives you good identification of the Quasars. Those would be great for testing that we will talk about this afternoon. And finally, the Lyman galaxies, we are expecting to find them, seven to basically where the luminosity distance caught us off. And Isaac has already spoken in depth about our techniques with the simulations we are doing. Just to borrow a couple of numbers if we had gotten five square degrees to minus 17 you would have literally thousands out beyond ridership nine and ten. And the last topic I want to touch on, the interplay between the searches and the method, we have three team members who have been thinking hard about this and others involved. This figure is from a paper that they had put on the archive and it's also out there. What this is showing basically is the ability to distinguish between different neutral fractions with about a 20 square degree survey and you can see as you get out past the few square, the Roman will be able to tell the difference between these by comparing the cross-correlation of neutral gas from Lyman alpha and those found with Roman. 1 centimeter and the sources. Just to close, re-ionization is the key transition and cosmic history. We have established important constraints with observations from the ground in the spectra from space. Roman will enable vast rides by combining the sensitivity about the atmosphere with you wide-field that is been here for an accessible. I will stop here and take questions. Thanks.

Thank you. We do have time for a couple of questions. The first one is, so far it's asking about the reference, the curves.

That is a paper that Isak Wold is working on. It presents the results from the first four fields of the survey. It is still in the process, but I'm hoping we will see it out by the end of 2020. It's a careful piece of work looking at multiple selections of that and really trying to nail down all of the possible uncertainties and getting the function and the indication.

Thanks. If there are more questions please go to the selected channel and we will continue the discussion over there. It's time to break. I'm going to pass it over. They will inform us of the schedule. Thanks everyone. Thanks to all of our speakers. That will conclude our morning session. We will now take a 25 minute break. We will reconvene at 12:30 p.m.,

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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